

MODELLING THE INDUSTRIAL PROPANE-PROPYLENE SPLITTER INCORPORATING A STEAM TURBINE DRIVEN HEAT PUMP

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Abstract

Propane-propylene (C3) fraction splitting by rectification is generally characterised by high energetic demand due to very low relative volatility of the fraction components. The petrochemical technology, to which the propylene product is dedicated, requires its high purity, therefore extensive number of equilibrium stages and a great reflux ratio are necessary when applying a conventional approach. Thus, incorporating a heat pump utilizing latent heat of compressed overhead product vapours in the column reboiler serves as a typical technological solution to the issue. In SLOVNAFT refinery, the heat pump compressor is driven by a condensation steam turbine. In this contribution, the effects of the system operation parameters alteration on steam consumption are studied. A rigorous steady state model simulating the heat pump performance was developed and subsequently used in parametric sensitivity studies. Results of the simulations were confronted with available process data. Model predictions were found to be in close agreement with the reported data. Hence, the model allows for its utilization as a reliable tool for the system performance assessment.

Introduction

A Fluid Catalytic Cracking Unit is amongst the most vital parts of a modern refinery¹. The FCC Unit processes heavy crude fractions while producing a wide range of lighter products of which the propane-propylene fraction classifies as one of the most technologically significant². This fraction is split into almost pure components via the propane-propylene splitter at the Propylene Section of the FCC unit. As propane and propylene form a close-boiling mixture³, energetic requirements of the column reboiler may exceed 1 MWh per 1 tonne of fraction⁴ and a significant amount of heat needs to be simultaneously exposed of in the overhead condenser when applying a conventional method of fraction splitting. Thus, in pursuit of decreasing the overall energetic demands, the Propylene section employs a system comprising a steam turbine driven heat pump which utilizes the latent heat of overhead products as a heat source in the column reboiler. However, this solution makes the system significantly more complicated in comparison to traditional rectifying which unearths the need for a more sophisticated approach and reliable modelling.

Modelled system description

A simplified version of the process-flow diagram of the modelled system is shown in Figure 1. During standard operation, preheated feedstock is delivered to the feed stage of the C3 splitter – tray rectification column. Distillate vapours leaving the head of column are led to the suction drum of heat pump compressor which protects the compressor from condensate droplets and compensates system pressure fluctuations. Vapour phase continues to the suction nozzle of the compressor driven by condensation turbine. Main part of the compressed vapours is led to the column reboiler where it condenses at the discharge pressure and the heat of condensation serves as heat supply for the column. Condensate is subsequently expanded to the head pressure level and delivered to the column head as external reflux. As a means of regulation, part of the compressed vapours is condensed in water cooler (HEX 1) and led to the suction drum. Liquid phase pumped from the bottom of the suction drum is partly exported as product flow to storage and partly delivered to the column as a second reflux flow. To avoid potential compressor surge during low feed rates, it is possible to by-pass part of the compressed vapours back to the suction drum, though this passage is closed during standard operation.

Object of study

The issue of refining industry energy intensity decrease has been the subject of numerous studies in recent years. In order to be able to predict the system energy requirements, it is inevitable to understand the behaviour of the described system. Thus, it was necessary to compose a reliable mathematical model reflecting the physical plant structure as shown in Figure 1 and based on both the laws of thermodynamics and mass and energy balances

together with heat and mass equations and economic considerations. Subsequently, composed model verification was a prerequisite for its utilization in economically aimed case studies.

Figure 1. Process-flow diagram of the modelled system with measurement points displayed

Mathematical modelling

The proposed mathematical model comprises rigorous computations based on MESH equations for each stage of the C3 splitter and characteristics-based mass and heat balances of the heat pump system. The concentration profile and molar flow rates throughout the column are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively, alongside the most important heat pump characteristics (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Concentration profiles along stages

Figure 3. Molar flow rates in rectification column

Figure 4a. Compressor polytropic head

Figure 4b. Compressor polytropic efficiency

Figure 4c. Compressor power requirements

Figure 4d. Turbine characteristics

Legend: The star marking in Figure 4 represents actual performance. The dash-dotted line in Figure 4a represents anti-surge line.

The proposed model was used to predict high-pressure steam consumption of condensation turbine in relation to the C3 fraction feed rate. Model predictions were confronted with provided process data collected during a one year period.

It is important to mention that there is no existing steam flow rate measuring at the time, therefore the steam consumption evaluation was based on the steam condensate flow rate. As can be seen in Figure 5, part of the steam condensate is allegedly being recirculated in the system as a means of condensate network regulation. Hence, the measured and model-based data differ by a constant of 2.5 t/h.

However, the trend in steam consumption is preserved as can be seen in the trending line slope (depicting specific steam consumption). Close agreement of measured and model based data can be observed in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Steam consumption of turbine in relation to feedstock flow rate

Figure 6. Steam consumption over the evaluated time period

Case study: Condensation pressure alteration analysis

Steam consumption of condensation turbines is proportional to pressure level in the condenser. To evaluate the impact of this matter, a case study aiming for condenser pressure level decrease was carried out. As shown in Figure 7, lowering of the pressure from actual 22 kPa (abs.) to 8 kPa reduces the specific steam consumption by approximately 0.04 kg/kg (steam/feedstock), resulting in saving over 400 kg/h of high-pressure steam during stable operation. This fact cuts the annual (8000 h) steam consumption by more than 3200 tonnes.

Figure 7. Specific steam consumption in relation to feedstock flow rate

Based on engineering studies conducted in 2012 and our design calculations, total capital expenses resulting from the necessary modifications should not exceed 300 000 €. Thus, depending on the actual cost of high-pressure steam, this proposal expects a payback period of 2.5 to 6 years as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Simple payback period in relation to steam price

Conclusion

This work provides an overview of developed mathematical model capable of predicting system performance. Flexibility of proposed model allows for carrying out various case studies, one of which aimed for analysis of potential savings gained by lowering of condensation pressure based on model-provided data. As was shown in this proposal, the system has a potential of lowering of the high-pressure steam consumption of the condensation turbine by approximately 400 kg/h. Depending on the actual cost of high-pressure steam, the capital investment related to proposed savings shows a payback period of less than four years for the majority of steam prices which may be found attractive for a plant of such size as SLOVNAFT. Since the full potential of the proposed model has not yet been reached, further case studies focusing on system energy intensity reduction are to be conducted.

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